

Fifteen species of Platygastriinae (Hymenoptera: Platygastriidae) new to the fauna of Poland

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PETER NEERUP BUHL¹

¹Troldhøjvej 3, DK-3310 Ølsted, Denmark, e-mail: pnbuhl@hotmail.com

²Museum of Natural History, University of Wrocław, Sienkiewicza 21, 50-335 Wrocław, Poland, e-mail: scydmaenus@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT. Fifteen species of Platygastriinae (Hymenoptera: Platygastriidae) new to the fauna of Poland.

New distributional records of fifteen species of Platygastriinae (Hymenoptera: Platygastriidae) are given, all reported for the first time from Poland: *Acerotella evanescens* (KIEFFER), *Amblyaspis crates* (WALKER), *Platygaster betulae* (KIEFFER), *P. inermis* WALKER, *P. marginata* THOMSON, *P. martii* BUHL, *P. otanes* WALKER, *P. taras* WALKER, *P. tuberosula* KIEFFER, *P. zigrida* BUHL, *Prosynoeps hybridum* (BUHL), *Synoeps breve* BUHL, *S. compressiventris* (SZABO), *S. hyllus* (WALKER), and *S. ronquisti* BUHL. The new records increase the number of Platygastriinae known to occur in Poland to 139 species.

KEY WORDS: Hymenoptera, Platygastroidea, Platygastriidae, Platygastriinae; faunistics, new records, Poland.

INTRODUCTION

GARBARCZYK (1997) listed from Poland 56 species of Platygastriinae (i.e., Platygastriidae excluding Scelionidae and Sceliotrachelidae, as accepted by most authors today). Since then, *Synoeps bialowiezaensis* BUHL, 2005 and *Platygaster polonica* BUHL & JAŁOSZYŃSKI, 2016a were described based on specimens known only from Poland, and *Inostemma kaponeni* BUHL, 2005 was described from Finland and Poland. Furthermore, sixteen species were recorded for the first time from Poland by BUHL & JAŁOSZYŃSKI (2016b), and the male of *Synoeps burgeri* BUHL, 2012, a species known so far only from the German female holotype, was discovered in Poland and described (BUHL & JAŁOSZYŃSKI 2016a). Most recently, BUHL & JAŁOSZYŃSKI (2017, 2018) discovered another 48 species previously not known to occur in Poland. As a result, the checklist of the Platygastriinae of Poland includes currently 124 species.

In the present study we give records of 15 species previously not known from Poland, further expanding our knowledge of this still poorly known wasp family.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Specimens were collected using a sweeping net, by the second author; all voucher specimens were dry mounted on points and deposited in the collection of the second author, Wrocław, Poland. The previously known distributional data are given after the Hymenoptera Online (<http://hol.osu.edu>) and a personal database of the first author. Data on known hosts, if available, are given after the same sources. We acknowledge Rafał Ruta and Marek Wanat (University of Wrocław) for participating in fieldwork that yielded so many new country records.

RESULTS

Acerotella evanescens (KIEFFER, 1914)

East Sudety Mts: [YR14] Gipsowa Góra env. ad Kietrz, grassland, 22.05.2018, 1 ♀; [YR14] Lubotyń ad Kietrz, large sandpit partly overgrown with low vegetation, 22.05.2018, 1 ♀.
Distribution: Germany, Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Latvia, Russia, Moldova. Host unknown.

Amblyaspis crates (WALKER, 1835)

East Sudety Mts: [YR14] Lubotyń ad Kietrz, large sandpit partly overgrown with low vegetation, 22.05.2018, 1 ♂.
Distribution: Great Britain, Ireland, Sweden, Spain. Host unknown.

Platygaster betulae (KIEFFER, 1916)

Lower Silesia: [XS37] Wrocław Świniary, meadow, on grass and *Tanacetum vulgare* L. near Widawa Riv., 23.08.2018, 2 ♀♀.
Distribution: Great Britain, Ireland, France, Germany, Switzerland, Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Mongolia. Host: the cecidomyiid fly *Semudobia betulae* (WINNERTZ) on *Betula* spp.

Platygaster inermis WALKER, 1836

East Sudety Mts: [YR14] Gipsowa Góra env. ad Kietrz, grassland, 22.05.2018, 3 ♀♀.
Distribution: Great Britain, Denmark, Finland. Host unknown.

Platygaster marginata THOMSON, 1859

East Sudety Mts: [YR14] Lubotyń ad Kietrz, large sandpit partly overgrown with low vegetation, 22.05.2018, 1 ♀.
Distribution: Ireland, Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Latvia, Mongolia. Host unknown.

Platygaster martii BUHL, 2003

East Sudety Mts: [YR14] Gipsowa Góra env. ad Kietrz, grassland, 22.05.2018, 2 ♀♀.
Distribution: Denmark, Finland, Latvia. Host unknown.

Platygaster otanes WALKER, 1836

East Sudety Mts: [YR14] Lubotyń ad Kietrz, large sandpit partly overgrown with low vegetation, 22.05.2018, 1 ♀.
Distribution: Great Britain, Ireland, Denmark, Sweden, Norway, Germany, Latvia, Spain, Mongolia. Host unknown.

Platygaster taras WALKER, 1836

East Sudety Mts: [YR14] Gipsowa Góra env. ad Kietrz, grassland, 22.05.2018, 1 ♂; [YR14] Lubotyń ad Kietrz, large sandpit partly overgrown with low vegetation, 22.05.2018, 1 ♀.
Distribution: so far known only from Great Britain. Host unknown.

Platygaster tuberosula KIEFFER, 1926

Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland: [CD63] Włocławek, pine forest, 22.06.2018, 1 ♀.

Distribution: Great Britain, Belgium, Germany, Denmark, Sweden, Canada. Hosts: the cecidomyiid flies *Sitodiplosis mosellana* (GÉHIN) (orange wheat blossom midge) and *Contarinia tritici* (KIRBY) (yellow wheat blossom midge) on wheat, and *Dasineura mali* KIEFFER (apple leaf-curling midge) on apple.

Platygaster zigrida BUHL, 2010

Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland: [CD63] Włocławek, pine forest, 07-08.09.2018, 1 ♀.

Distribution: Germany, Denmark, Finland, Latvia. Host unknown.

Prosynopeas hybridum (BUHL, 1994)

Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland: [CD63] Włocławek, pine forest, 22.06.2018, 1 ♀.

Distribution: Great Britain, Denmark, Norway, Sweden, Finland, Latvia; host: *Cecidomyia pini* (DE GEER) on pines.

Synopeas breve BUHL, 1998

Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland: [CD63] Włocławek, pine forest, 22.06.2018, 1 ♀.

Distribution: Ireland, Great Britain, Germany, Norway, Sweden, Finland, Latvia. Host unknown.

Synopeas compressiventris (SZABÓ, 1981)

Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland: [CD63] Włocławek, pine forest, 07-08.09.2018, 1 ♀.

Distribution: so far known only from Hungary. Host unknown.

Synopeas hyllus (WALKER, 1836)

East Sudety Mts: [YR14] Lubotyń ad Kietrz, large sandpit partly overgrown with low vegetation, 22.05.2018, 1 ♀.

Distribution: Ireland, Germany, Denmark, Sweden, Norway, Finland, Mongolia. Host unknown.

Synopeas ronquisti BUHL, 2010

Wielkopolsko-Kujawska Lowland: [CD63] Włocławek, pine forest, 07-08.09.2018, 1 ♀.

Distribution: previously known only from Germany and Sweden. Host unknown.

DISCUSSION

The knowledge of the Polish fauna of Platygastriinae, a group largely neglected in the past, has recently considerably increased. GARBARCZYK (1997) listed only 56 spp.; this number is now nearly 2.5 times higher and comprises 139 species. BUHL & JAŁOSZYŃSKI (2018) estimated that even over 250 species can be expected to occur in Poland, based on the distribution of European taxa and availability of their hosts and

habitats. Consequently, it can be predicted that intensification of collecting will yield more interesting discoveries, including species new to science, as such have already been found in Poland. The current study demonstrates that grasslands and sandpits in SW Poland, especially those characterized by an intense insulation (e.g., Gipsowa Góra, Lubotyń), are promising habitats to search for previously unrecorded species. However, even relatively species-poor pine forests (or rather monoculture plantations) of Central Poland (as those in Włocławek) are very poorly studied and can be inhabited by yet undiscovered platygastrines.

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STRESZCZENIE

Piętnaście gatunków Platygastrinae (Hymenoptera: Platygastridae) nowych dla fauny Polski

Od końca XX wieku liczba gatunków Platygastrinae znanych z terytorium Polski wzrosła z 56 do aktualnie znanych 139. Piętnaście gatunków zostało podanych jako nowe dla Polski w niniejszej pracy: *Acerotella evanescens* (KIEFFER), *Amblyaspis crates* (WALKER), *Platygaster betulae* (KIEFFER), *P. inermis* WALKER, *P. marginata* THOMSON, *P. martii* BUHL, *P. otanes* WALKER, *P. taras* WALKER, *P. tuberosula* KIEFFER, *P. zigrida* BUHL, *Prosynopeas hybridum* (BUHL), *Synopeas breve* BUHL, *S. compressiventris* (SZABÓ), *S. hyllus* (WALKER) i *S. ronquisti* BUHL. Część z nich odkryto na otwartych, wygrzanych, trawiastych lub pokrytych niską roślinnością zielną i krzewami stanowiskach Sudetów Wschodnich o piaszczystym lub gipsowym podłożu. Jednak również monokultury sosnowe Kujaw pozostają bardzo słabo zbadane pod kątem fauny Platygastrinae; z takich stanowisk w okolicach Włocławka pozyskano sześć z gatunków podanych w niniejszej pracy jako nowe dla Polski. Oznacza to, że poznanie Platygastrinae Polski wymaga gruntownego zbadania nawet środowisk o stosunkowo niskim bogactwie gatunków roślin; wcześniejsze prace wskazują też centra miast jako środowisko życia wielu słabo poznanych parazytoidów. Z pewnością dalsze prace znacząco zwiększą liczbę znanych z Polski Platygastrinae, która powinna być zbliżona (lub nawet większa) od tej znanej z dobrze zbadanych krajów, jak Dania czy Wielka Brytania, gdzie odnotowano przeszło 200 gatunków.

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